

CAPACITY–BUILDING IS AN ESSENTIAL CONDITION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WATER SUPPLY

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the urgent problem of further development of drinking water supply and sewerage systems in settlements. The issues of improving the training of qualified personnel in the field of water supply and sewerage are considered.*

Introduction. One of the main conditions for achieving the parameters outlined in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 is the intensive growth of the population, the development of settlements and ensuring an improvement in the quality of life of the population with access to clean drinking water.

The modern water supply system is a complex of complex engineering structures for the extraction, processing, storage, supply and distribution of water between consumers. The requirements for the quality of water supply system projects are constantly increasing. This is due to an increase in the number of water consumers, regulating tanks, unregulated water consumption, constantly occurring transients, development and reconstruction of systems and structures, possible peak loads and failures of system elements. Water supply systems are becoming even more complex due to the connection of new and new sites for the delivery of water to newly emerging water consumers. The internal wear and tear of existing networks and structures, communications and equipment has the most noticeable effect on the operation of engineering networks. The technical condition of the existing engineering systems poses a significant threat of a social and economic nature.

As is known, with an increase in the number of water consumers, regulating tanks, unregulated water consumption, constantly occurring transients, development and reconstruction of systems and structures, possible peak loads and failures of system elements, the need to improve methods of calculation and operation of water supply systems is increasing.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2910 dated 04/20/2017 "On the program for the integrated development and modernization of drinking water supply and sewerage systems for 2017-2021" notes that, during the years of independence, significant work has been carried out in Uzbekistan to improve the provision of high-quality drinking water to the population. In particular, in the last six years alone, about 13 thousand km of water pipelines and water supply networks, more than 1.6 thousand water intake wells, as well as 1.4 thousand water towers and reservoirs have been built and

reconstructed. As a result, numerous settlements that did not have access to drinking water were provided with water supply that meets modern requirements for water quality and safety.

At the same time, there are still a number of acute unresolved problems related to the provision of high-quality drinking water to settlements. The constant increase in the population, the construction of new residential areas, the expansion of cities and settlements require the adoption of effective measures to radically improve the guaranteed water supply system, aimed at modernizing and advancing the development of water intake structures, aqueducts, pumping stations, distribution nodes and water supply networks based on the active introduction of modern energy-saving and resource-saving technologies. In solving such complex problems, of course, the main role is given to personnel training, which is the basis for the sustainable development of the entire water supply system.

Thus, at present, in conditions of a shortage of local water supply sources and the increasing use of group water pipes, the issue of providing personnel for the design, construction and operation of water supply and sewerage systems is acute. The main directions of further development in solving water supply problems are defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 40400 "On additional measures for the development of drinking water supply and sewerage systems in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated 11/30/18. Thus, the Decree instructs the Ministry of Housing and Communal Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with a number of Ministries, including the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Education and others, to submit proposals to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan to improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel of water supply and sewerage enterprises.

Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers (TIAME) is one of the main regional centers for training specialists in a wide range of fields, including water supply, which is famous for its historical traditions and schools. Thus, the training of specialists in the TIAME on water supply, in particular, in rural settlements, began back in the 70s. In 1961, the Department of Agricultural Water Supply and Irrigation was opened at TIAME (now part of the Department of Ecology and Water Resources Management), where a few years later certified specialists with higher technical education began to graduate. Currently, specialists in the bachelor's and master's degree programs are being trained at this department. Every year, about 40 students who undergo practical training at water supply facilities perform qualifying graduation work on real objects for the design justification, selection and design of water supply systems in settlements.

Historical background: in the 70s of the last century, the construction of residential buildings began in the newly created settlements of Golodnaya and later Karshi steppe. The construction of new settlements assumed the need to provide the population with drinking water, i.e. the creation of water supply and

sewerage systems. In the same years, the construction of the first Group water pipelines in the Republic began, such as Zaminsky, Sanzarsky, etc. Currently, new group water pipelines have been built, continue to be built and are being designed in almost all regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in Karakalpakstan to provide drinking water to the population.

Since the 2018-2019 academic year, TIAME has been recruiting students for undergraduate studies "Engineering structures of water supply systems". The objects of bachelor's activity in the chosen field are: drinking water supply and sewerage systems that meet the needs of the population and industrial facilities, their operation, pasture water supply system and sources, water supply technologies and equipment, design of wastewater treatment plants. The curriculum for the direction includes conducting production and qualification graduation practices that take into account the specifics of the direction. In special disciplines, laboratory work is provided on models in the laboratory of the department. A bachelor, after completing his studies in the field, can continue his studies in the chosen specialization for 2 years.

From the academic year 2020-2021, it is planned to enroll students in the master's degree program in the above-mentioned specialization.

Educational and methodological developments carried out at the department include textbooks, manuals and methodological guidelines for performing independent work, course projects, graduation papers, laboratory work, programs for performing calculations of networks and structures for water supply, improving water quality, sewerage and wastewater treatment. Textbooks and manuals prepared at TIAME have repeatedly been determined the winners of the republican competition for the best educational literature.

At the department "Ecology and management of water resources" along with educational and methodological work and training of specialists of a wide profile for the industrial sector, research work is underway to find scientific solutions to water supply problems based on state budget and household contractual works, grants. Purposeful work is underway to train scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, more than 40 masters', PhD and doctoral dissertations have been defended on the development of scientific foundations for the development of water supply and irrigation of pastures, as well as on improving methods for calculating systems and structures for water supply and distribution in water supply complexes.

A separate area of activity at the department is the professional development of specialists working in the field of water supply and sewerage. To improve their skills in the field of "Engineering structures of water supply systems", educational and methodological complexes have been prepared for a number of disciplines: "Technologies and structures for water purification", "Automation of water supply system structures", "Water delivery and distribution systems".

The existing agreements on Cooperation with GUPT water utility and with the Ministry of Housing and Communal Services allow us to jointly resolve

issues related to conducting industrial and pre-graduation qualification practice, solve the issue of graduate employment, organize field classes at existing water supply and sewerage systems, etc.

Conclusions: It should be emphasized that, as the results of the analysis show, the state of development (or rather lagging) of water supply systems, taking into account the upcoming volume of work, does not fully meet the requirements of today. It is necessary to develop integration mechanisms between higher education institutions and industry enterprises, to strengthen the interest and participation of production in personnel training.

Special issues of cooperation should include the employment of graduates and support for scientific and innovative activities by forming a bank of problems existing in production and a portfolio of orders, providing a base for research based on partnership.

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